

Original Research

Comprehensive Econometric Modeling of Commodity and Cryptocurrency Impacts on the S&P 500 Index

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Received 24 December 2024 Revised 27 July 2025 Accepted 30 July 2025

Abstract

This study proposes an empirical econometric approach that emphasizes the integration of diverse financial assets to enhance market trend prediction. While the regression method employed is based on the conventional Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique, the novelty of this work lies in the strategic combination of key global commodities oil, gold, silver (SLV), and natural gas (GAS) with Bitcoin (BTC), a major cryptocurrency rarely examined jointly with traditional assets. By incorporating these variables as predictors of the S&P 500 index (SP), the study delivers a more comprehensive perspective on cross-market interactions. The model is further evaluated through tests for serial autocorrelation, correlation structure, specification errors, and predictive accuracy. Empirical results reveal that oil, gold, and Bitcoin significantly boost the S&P 500 index, while silver negatively impacts it, reflecting its safe-haven role. Natural gas shows no significant effect. The model's strong explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.93$) validates the Comprehensive Econometric Modeling for explaining index dynamics.

Keywords: Commodities, cryptocurrency, econometrics, financial markets, global economics, S&P 500 Index.

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Introduction

Due to the inherent nature of the stock market and its sensitivity to political and social events, are also heavily affected by fluctuations. in key economic variables (Heydarpour et al., 2025). Understanding the relationships between economic factors and major market indices, like the S&P 500, is essential for effectively managing the risks posed by these fluctuations. Due to the numerous influential factors and the complexity of their interactions, more thorough analyses and precise modeling are required to identify these interdependencies and evaluate their impact on stock markets. This allows investors to make more confident and accurate predictions in the market. In this regard, the main objective of this study is to examine the simultaneous effects of key commodities and Bitcoin on the S&P 500 index. it was selected due to its role as a globally recognized benchmark that reflects broader shifts in economic sentiment and transmits spillover effects across asset classes and regional markets. In this context, key commodities such as oil, gold, silver, and natural gas along with Bitcoin, are examined as explanatory variables. These assets are globally traded and closely linked to macroeconomic fundamentals such as inflation, growth, and financial uncertainty. Their dynamic interaction with equity markets makes them critical for understanding the underlying drivers of stock index movements. The novelty of this research lies in its comprehensive model, which includes traditional commodities such as silver, gold, oil, and natural gas, as well as Bitcoin as an independent variable in the analysis. The study then employs various econometric tests, including tests for serial correlation, the Ramsey RESET test, and model stability analysis. These tests evaluate both the predictive power and explanatory accuracy of the model. Key economic parameters include significant commodities like oil, gold, silver, and natural gas, significantly influencing stock market behavior due to their complex relationships with various industries. Price fluctuations in commodities can profoundly impact financial markets and the global economy. It is worth mentioning that recent developments in the financial world, such as the increasing importance of cryptocurrencies and their effects on market indices, highlight the need to reevaluate traditional analytical frameworks.

As the first and most prominent cryptocurrency, Bitcoin has become a crucial factor in the analysis of financial markets. This development underscores the need for a more comprehensive model incorporating commodity-based approaches while accounting for the impact of emerging financial markets, such as cryptocurrencies. This is crucial for understanding market dynamics and predicting behavior. In contrast, traditional models often focus on the effects of specific commodities or analyze Bitcoin in isolation. They do not consider the combined impact of these two asset classes within a single framework. Accordingly, this study seeks to address the following research question: To what extent do traditional commodities and Bitcoin jointly influence the behavior of the S&P 500 index?

As a result, the approach in this study not only enhances our understanding of the behavior of the S&P 500 but also equips financial analysts and policymakers with new tools to make more informed decisions during periods of intense market volatility. Figure 1 displays the model's conceptual framework.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Model

Literature review

Impact of Commodities on Financial Markets

Since the economy operates globally, fluctuations and various events in the global markets can significantly impact stock market movements. Consequently, numerous researchers have investigated the influence of essential commodities on other vital economic variables. Ghanbari et al. (2022) examined how the dollar, oil, and gold prices affect the Iranian stock market, highlighting the significance of these factors. Shabbir et al.(2020) examined oil on the Pakistani stock market. Their findings showed that fluctuations in oil prices significantly influenced market movements. Their study also included an analysis of the effects of the dollar and gold on the Shanghai stock market, focusing on the COVID-19 crisis period. Dutta (2019) conducted an innovative study examining the influence of silver on the market and its subsequent effects on the stock performance of solar energy companies. This research introduces a novel perspective on this relationship, contributing valuable insights. Sujit and Kumar (2011) thoroughly analyzed the intricate dynamics among oil and gold prices, exchange rates, and market returns. Their research provides significant insights into the interconnected nature of these financial markets. Kumar et al. (2021) investigated the interactions between gold, exchange rate, oil price, and natural gas with the Indian stock market, utilizing evidence from a nonlinear asymmetric ARDL model. Narayan et al. (2020), in their research conducted against the challenging backdrop of the COVID-19 pandemic, investigated the

Japanese yen's relationship with the Japanese stock market, providing insights into how currency fluctuations impacted stock market performance. Fooeik et al. (2022) investigated the Nasdaq index dependence on palladium, oil, and gold and found that gold and oil significantly impacted this index. Tursoy and Faisal (2018) in their study on the Turkish stock market, investigated the fluctuations in gold and oil prices' impact on this market, using Granger causality tests to reveal short-term, long-term, and common one-way causalities between gold and stock prices.

Raza et al. (2016) analyzed how changes in gold and oil prices affect stock markets, highlighting that these markets are vulnerable to negative news and events that lead to economic instability. Bhuni and Mukhuti (2013) investigated domestic gold fluctuation's impact on the Indian stock market, providing insights into how gold price movements influence market performance. Blose and Shieh (1995) explored the correlation between gold prices and the value of gold mining shares, noting that gold mine value depends on gold yield, production costs, gold reserves, and the ratio of assets unrelated to gold price risk. Arfaoui and Ben Rejeb (2017) explored the interdependence among oil, gold, the dollar, and stock markets, revealing significant direct and indirect relationships between these variables. Mitchell and Mulherin (1994) investigated the connection between daily reports from the Dow Jones and different metrics of market activity in the securities market, such as trading volume and market returns. Nordin et al. (2014) studied the effects of interest rates, commodity prices, and exchange rates on the Malaysian stock market. Gatfaoui (2016) examined the effectiveness of the stock market from oil and gas and focused on how these commodities influence market performance. Mao et al. (2024) investigated the relationship between the COVID-19 pandemic, stock markets, and crude oil markets regarding returns and volatility spillovers. Salem et al. (2025) examined how the Russian–Ukrainian conflict affects international financial markets, particularly oil price fluctuations and their impact on stock market performance in oil-importing and oil-exporting countries from 2017 to 2023. Yaya et al. (2021) explored the long-term interactions between daily prices, stock market trends, and fear indicators related to gold and silver. By employing the sophisticated Fractional Cointegrating Vector Autoregression (FCVAR) model, the study provides a deep analysis of these relationships, offering valuable insights into how fear-driven market factors impact the behavior of precious metals and stock markets over time. Hanitha et al. (2024) analyzed the relationship between commodity prices such as gold, gas, tin, silver, nickel, and oil and the FTSE Indonesia stock market index. Using secondary data from January 2020 to December 2023, the study applied multiple linear regression to evaluate how fluctuations in commodity prices affect the index's value, providing insights for investors and policymakers.

Impact of Cryptocurrencies on Financial Markets

Ünvan (2021) investigated Bitcoin's impact on the Turkish, Chinese, Japanese, and United States markets. Maghyreh and Abdoh (2021) studied the time-frequency relationship between Bitcoin and global stock markets, finding a long-term positive correlation between Bitcoin and stock markets, which diminishes significantly when comparing annual to monthly investment horizons. Wang et al. (2020) investigated the stock market and Bitcoin relationships, finding that Bitcoin depends on fluctuations in Dow Jones and the S&P 500. Tiwari et al. (2019) analyzed the dynamic conditional

correlation between stock markets and digital currencies, concluding that digital currencies could play a significant role in diversifying investment portfolios. Meela et al. (2024) examined the influence of cryptocurrency on investment portfolios, utilizing the services of currency brokers at Yellow Card Company in Tanzania. Their research emphasized price fluctuations, market trends, and volatility metrics. Nguyen (2022) examined Bitcoin's effect on the stock market during COVID-19, focusing on how cryptocurrency fluctuations affected market indices. Wang et al. (2022) studied The Connection Between the Stock Market and the Digital Assets Currency Market, highlighting the usefulness of their findings for regulatory authorities and offering rational investors insights into hedging strategies. Their research investigates the dependencies among oil prices, gold, the U.S. dollar, and stock markets, identifying direct and indirect linkages between these variables.

Shoetan and FAMILONI (2024) provided an in-depth review of blockchain technology's growing influence across various industries, primarily focusing on its role in promoting sustainable logistics in the oil sector. By examining its adoption in Nigeria and the USA, the study explores how blockchain enhances efficiency, increases transparency, and supports environmental sustainability in supply chain management. Their findings highlight blockchain's potential to address key logistical and ecological challenges within the industry. The study by Seetharaman et al. (2017) explores factors contributing to Bitcoin's momentum in global finance and its potential to disrupt traditional fiat currencies, particularly the USD. Key variables include regulation surrounding Bitcoin, its technology, the economy, and its use as a currency. Aliyev and Eylasov (2025) examined the impact of financial indices, currency values, and commodities on cryptocurrencies. Using data from 2017 to 2024, this study confirms a long-run cointegration relationship. Findings show that the US dollar index negatively affects Bitcoin and Ethereum, while the NASDAQ-100 index positively influences Bitcoin but not Ethereum. Oil prices positively affect both, whereas gold shows no significant relationship.

Research gaps

While previous research has investigated the effects of commodities and Bitcoin on stock market indices separately, there has yet to be a comprehensive analysis that explores the impact of Bitcoin alongside selected key commodities within an integrated framework. This notable research gap underscores the need for more holistic approaches to enhance understanding of the interactions between financial markets and economic indicators.

Methodology

Given the significant role the stock market plays in the economy, it provides a valuable snapshot of a country's economic conditions. Thus, analyzing the stock market is a logical approach to understanding the broader financial landscape. The stock market reflects the overall state of the economy through various indices, each designed to track different sectors or industries. For instance, to assess the performance of the chemical industry, one might refer to the relevant industry index within the stock market (such as the chemical index), which offers a clear and focused view of that sector's health. The S&P

500 index is a significant benchmark Standard & Poor's created, representing the 500 largest companies in the U.S. stock market. The index's fluctuations are driven by changes in the market values of these companies, with larger companies exerting a more significant influence. Over time, the composition of the S&P 500 evolves as companies are added or removed based on criteria such as market capitalization, the percentage of floating shares, and average liquidity. Equation (1) illustrates the calculation method for the S&P 500 index.

$$S\&S\ 500\ index\ level = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n p_i Q_i}{divisor} \quad Eq\ (1)$$

p = price

Q = free float shares

divisor

= A variable that can change with net dividends and other variables affecting the index

This study employs the OLS method due to its simplicity, interpretability, and broad applicability in financial market analysis. OLS is a widely used econometric approach that provides efficient and reliable estimations while minimizing unnecessary model complexity. Its flexibility makes it well-suited for capturing relationships in global financial datasets without additional structural assumptions. The regression model specified in Equation 2 will be estimated using EViews 13.

$$S\&P\ 500\ (SP) = \alpha + \beta_1 oil + \beta_2 gold + \beta_3 slv + \beta_4 btc + \beta_5 gas + u_t \quad Eq\ (2)$$

sp *s&p 500 index*

gold *gold price*

slv *silver price*

oil *oil price*

btc *bitcoin price*

gas *gas price*

Findings and Discussion

The dataset utilized in this study covers January 2017 to March 2021 in the monthly time frame, with all data obtained from Finance.yahoo.com. The use of monthly data is economically justified and aligns with the study's objective of capturing medium- and long-term financial linkages.

As shown in Figure 2, the area charts depict the price trends of each examined variable, offering a visual overview of their fluctuations throughout the study period. Table 1 illustrates the descriptive statistics relevant to the dataset under consideration, offering a

detailed summary of their key statistical characteristics. The table highlights that BTC exhibits substantial volatility and irregular price movements, as evidenced by a Jarque-Bera test value of 285.139, strongly indicating a deviation from normality. The SP is on the edge of normality, with a Jarque-Bera value of 6.033 and a probability of 0.049, suggesting mild deviations from a normal distribution. In contrast, commodity variables such as SLV, Oil, and Gold demonstrate lower volatility than Bitcoin (BTC) and generally align more closely with a normal distribution. also, the variable's correlation matrix is presented in Table 2, illustrating their relationships.

Figure 2. Area charts of studied variables

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for the variables, including measures of central tendency, volatility, and normality tests

	SP	SLV	OIL	GAS	GOLD	BTC
Mean	2898.039	19.059	56.255	3.020	1506.549	10029.760
Median	2824.000	17.000	55.000	3.000	1410.000	7780.000
Maximum	3973.000	28.000	84.000	6.000	1968.000	58919.000
Minimum	2279.000	14.000	19.000	2.000	1192.000	970.000
Std. Dev.	404.550	4.356	12.379	0.836	258.406	10510.490
Skewness	0.838	0.778	-0.301	1.413	0.391	3.031
Kurtosis	3.181	2.097	3.399	5.823	1.526	12.872
Jarque-Bera	6.033	6.875	1.110	33.911	5.920	285.139
Probability	0.049	0.032	0.574	0.000	0.052	0.000
Sum	147800.000	972.000	2869.000	154.000	76834.000	511518.000
Sum Sq. Dev.	8183020.000	948.824	7661.686	34.980	3338687.000	552000000
Observations	51.000	51.000	51.000	51.000	51.000	51.000

Table 2. Correlation between variables

	SP	SLV	OIL	GAS	GOLD	BTC
SP	1.000	0.647	0.339	0.438	0.753	0.808
SLV	0.647	1.000	0.111	0.291	0.870	0.393
OIL	0.339	0.111	1.000	0.544	-0.124	0.472
GAS	0.438	0.291	0.544	1.000	0.118	0.596
GOLD	0.753	0.870	-0.124	0.118	1.000	0.459
BTC	0.808	0.393	0.472	0.596	0.459	1.000

Initial model estimation

In this section, we begin with the initial estimation of the model using EViews 13 software. The regression equation, presented in Equation (3), serves as the starting point for the analysis. This initial estimation is essential for laying the groundwork for subsequent steps, including model diagnostics and refinement. The results from this stage offer a preliminary understanding of how the selected commodities and Bitcoin influence the S&P 500 index, setting the stage for deeper investigation in the following sections of the study.

$$sp = 599.62 + 9.636 \text{ OIL} + 1.44 \text{ GOLD} - 31.425 \text{ SLV} + 0.013 \text{ BTC} + 31.313 \text{ GAS} + u_t \quad \text{Eq (3)}$$

Table 3 presents coefficient estimation, standard errors, t-statistics, and associated probabilities.

Table 3. Regression results

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
SLV	-31.425	13.101	-2.399	0.021
GOLD	1.440	0.252	5.724	0.000
OIL	9.636	2.615	3.685	0.001
BTC	0.013	0.004	3.596	0.001
GAS	31.313	37.197	0.842	0.404
C	559.620	297.958	1.878	0.067

The empirical results reveal statistically significant relationships for the majority of the explanatory variables, with the exception of natural GAS, which presents a p-value exceeding the conventional 5% significance threshold, indicating its effect on the S&P 500 index is not statistically discernible. Notably, OIL, GOLD, and BTC demonstrate robust statistical significance, each with p-values well below 0.05, underscoring their meaningful and reliable influence on the index. The estimated coefficient for SLV is negative and statistically significant, reflecting an inverse association with the index, consistent with its typical role as a safe-haven asset during periods of market uncertainty. Conversely, while the coefficient for GAS is positive, it lacks statistical significance,

suggesting that fluctuations in natural gas prices do not materially affect the index within the studied timeframe.

The results in Table 4 show that the model demonstrates strong explanatory power, with an R-squared of 0.877 and an Adjusted R-squared of 0.864, indicating that the included variables jointly explain approximately 86% of the variation in the S&P 500 index. The high F-statistic (64.365) and its p-value of 0.000 further confirm the overall significance of the model. These findings emphasize the model's robustness in capturing key drivers of market behavior when both traditional commodities and emerging digital assets such as Bitcoin are integrated. Unlike prior studies that examined assets individually, this comprehensive approach provides deeper insights into cross-asset interactions and market dynamics. Moreover, the model offers practical implications for portfolio diversification, particularly during periods of market uncertainty. However, the Durbin-Watson statistic (0.963) points to positive autocorrelation in the residuals, suggesting the need for methodological refinement through dynamic techniques to improve model accuracy.

Table 4. Initial Regression Analysis Results

Statistic	Value/probability
R-squared	0.877
Adjusted R-squared	0.864
S.E. of regression	149.358
Sum squared resid	1003850.000
Log likelihood	-324.498
F-statistic	64.365
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000
Mean dependent var	2898.039
S.D. dependent var	404.550
Akaike info criterion	12.961
Schwarz criterion	13.188
Hannan-Quinn criter.	13.048
Durbin-Watson stat	0.963

Serial Correlation LM Test

Additional tests like the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM and Chow break Test have been implemented to confirm positive autocorrelation. As shown in Table 5, both tests indicate significant autocorrelation in the residuals, as evidenced by the low p-values for the F-statistic and Chi-Square tests at each lag level. The results suggest the need for model adjustments to address serial correlation.

Table 5. Results of the Serial Correlation LM Test at 2 and 3 lags for the initial model

Test Type	Statistics	Value/probability
Serial Correlation LM Test at 2 lags	F-statistic	8.036031
	Obs*R-squared	13.87585
	Prob. F (2,43)	0.0011
	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.001
Serial Correlation LM Test at 3 lags	F-statistic	5.372853
	Obs*R-squared	14.1443
	Prob. F (3,42)	0.0032
	Prob. Chi-Square (3)	0.0027

Chow break Test

In this section, we examine the points where a structural break is likely to have occurred, as indicated in Figure 3, by conducting a Chow breakpoint test.

Figure 3. Actual Residuals of the Model, highlighting potential points of possible structural breaks

As indicated in Table 6, the results show significant structural breaks at both points, as evidenced by the low p-values for the F-statistic and Chi-Square tests. Therefore, the findings from the Chow Breakpoint and autocorrelation tests underscore the importance of enhancing the model, potentially by including dummy variables or other adjustments.

Table 6. Results of the Chow Breakpoint Test for Structural Breaks in August 2018 and March 2020

Statistics	Value/probability for 2018M08	Value/probability for 2020M03
Prob. F (6,39)	0.0488	0.0013
Prob. Chi-Square (6)	0.0150	0.0001
Prob. Chi-Square (6)	0.0281	0.0001

Model Refinement Using Dummy Variables

In this section, the model is refined to address the structural breaks identified by the Chow Breakpoint test and the serial correlation detected in the residuals. dummy variables are introduced to capture significant shifts in the data, accounting for the effects of external events or regime changes. Tables 7 and 8 present the regression model results after incorporating dummy variables.

Table 7 highlights that the inclusion of dummy variables significantly enhances the model's explanatory power. Both dummy variables are statistically significant (DUMMY: 267.62, $p < 0.001$; DUMMY01: -149.50, $p = 0.016$), indicating the presence of structural breaks. Key predictors such as Oil (7.485, $p < 0.001$), Gold (1.460, $p < 0.001$), and Bitcoin (0.009, $p < 0.001$) exhibit strong and significant effects on the S&P 500, while Silver shows a significant negative impact. Natural Gas was excluded due to its lack of statistical significance. Overall, the modified model offers a more accurate depiction of market dynamics by accounting for structural shifts.

Table 7. Regression results show coefficients, standard errors, t-statistics, and p-values for each variable in the modified model

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
SLV	-32.166	9.224	-3.487	0.001
GOLD	1.460	0.164	8.919	0.000
OIL	7.485	1.858	4.028	0.000
BTC	0.009	0.002	4.140	0.000
DUMMY	267.621	40.695	6.576	0.000
DUMMY01	-149.503	59.820	-2.499	0.016
C	731.282	186.331	3.925	0.000

As shown in Table 8, the final model demonstrates a strong fit, with an R-squared of 0.942 and an Adjusted R-squared of 0.934, indicating that over 93% of the variation in the dependent variable is effectively explained. The high F-statistic (118.090, $p = 0.000$) confirms the overall significance of the model, while the Durbin-Watson value (2.043) suggests no evidence of autocorrelation. These improvements underscore the effectiveness of incorporating dummy variables in capturing structural shifts and enhancing model reliability. The results not only validate the model's robustness but also

support the study's broader goal of bridging traditional and emerging asset classes, offering valuable insights into their joint influence on financial markets. Equation 4 shows the model's final estimation.

$$sp = 731.282 + 7.485 OIL + 1.46 GOLD - 32.166 SLV + 0.009 BTC + 267.621DUMMY - 149.503DUMMY01 + u_t \quad Eq \quad (4)$$

Table 8. Final estimation of the regression model after adding a dummy variable

Statistic	Value/probability
R-squared	0.942
Adjusted R-squared	0.934
S.E. of regression	104.278
Sum squared resid	478451.000
Log likelihood	-305.601
F-statistic	118.090
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000
Mean dependent var	2898.039
S.D. dependent var	404.550
Akaike info criterion	12.259
Schwarz criterion	12.524
Hannan-Quinn criter.	12.360
Durbin-Watson stat	2.043

Table 9. Results of the Serial Correlation LM Test at 2 and 3 lags for the final model

Test Type	Statistics	Value/probability
Serial Correlation LM Test at 2 lags	F-statistic	1.006
	Obs*R-squared	2.332
	Prob. F (2,42)	0.374
	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.311
Serial Correlation LM Test at 3 lags	F-statistic	0.940
	Obs*R-squared	3.284
	Prob. F (3,41)	0.429
	Prob. Chi-Square (3)	0.349

Serial Correlation LM Test for the final model

In this part, we tested the final model for autocorrelation using the Serial Correlation LM Test at 2 and 3 lags. Table 9 indicates no significant serial correlation, as the p-values for the F-statistic and Chi-Square tests are above the typical 0.05 threshold.

Ramsey RESET test

In this section, the Ramsey RESET test is performed to check for the model's correct specification. the results in Table 10 indicate that neither the F-statistic nor the Likelihood

Ratio is statistically significant at the 5% level. This implies that incorporating nonlinear combinations of the fitted values does not meaningfully enhance the explanatory power of the model. Therefore, the current specification appears to be appropriate, and there is no substantial evidence of omitted nonlinear relationships. These findings reinforce the internal consistency of the model and support the validity of the linear structure adopted in this analysis.

Table 10. Ramsey RESET Test Results

Statistics	Value	Probability
F-statistic	1.246	0.298
Likelihood ratio	2.939	0.229

The CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares tests

The CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares tests are diagnostic tools used to assess the stability of a regression model over time.

The findings derived from the CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares evaluations, as shown in Figure 4, indicate that the model exhibits structural stability over the analyzed period. Specifically, the blue line remains consistently within the red confidence bands, suggesting no significant structural breaks or instability in the regression model. This implies that the model's coefficients are stable and robust, further supporting its validity for the dataset.

Figure 4. CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares tests results

In sample prediction

In this section, we evaluate the models' forecasting accuracy using the key performance metrics shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The model's forecasting performance

Based on a forecast evaluation using 51 observations from January 2017 to March 2021, the model yielded promising accuracy metrics. The Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) was 96.86 and the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was 74.89, indicating a relatively small deviation between predicted and actual values. Moreover, the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and its symmetric counterpart (MAPE) were 2.59% and 2.58%, respectively, suggesting a high level of predictive accuracy. The Theil Inequality Coefficient (U1) was calculated at 0.0166, which is close to zero and reflects a strong overall fit. A breakdown of Theil's components revealed that there was no systematic bias in the predictions (Bias Proportion = 0), and that nearly all forecast errors were attributed to imperfect correlation between the forecasted and actual values (Covariance Proportion \approx 0.98). Taken together, these results suggest that the initial model, despite not incorporating structural corrections, was capable of providing reasonably accurate forecasts of the S&P 500 index.

Conclusion

This study introduced a comprehensive econometric framework by integrating traditional commodities and Bitcoin to enhance the explanatory power of U.S. stock market behavior, offering more profound insights into asset interdependencies and market dynamics. First, the regression model was fitted by introducing oil, natural gas, gold, silver, and Bitcoin as independent variables and the S&P index as a dependent variable. Next, several econometric tests, including the Serial Correlation LM test, Ramsey RESET test, Chow break test, CUSUM, and CUSUM of squares tests, were conducted to evaluate the model's explanatory power, correct specification, etc. The findings demonstrate a

significant positive association between the S&P 500 index and oil, gold, and Bitcoin prices, where these variables directly correspond with rises in the index and vice versa. Conversely, a reverse correlation was found between the silver prices and the index. The analysis reveals an insignificant association between natural gas prices and the index. It is worth noting that the model with an R-squared value of 0.94 can effectively explain the index's behavior. These findings offer a robust framework for integrating traditional commodities and digital assets, enhancing the accuracy of market forecasts and supporting more informed investment decisions. By revealing the nuanced interdependencies among these asset classes, the study also provides valuable insights for policymakers and regulators, facilitating the development of adaptive macroprudential policies and strategic planning in response to the growing influence of decentralized financial instruments.

Recommendations

Investors and policymakers should consider the significant influence of traditional commodities and cryptocurrencies on financial markets when developing portfolio strategies and regulatory frameworks. Given the demonstrated impact of oil, gold, silver, natural gas, and Bitcoin on the S&P 500 index, market participants can enhance diversification by integrating these assets into investment decision-making. Additionally, future research should explore more advanced econometric techniques, such as spatial econometrics, to examine regional dependencies and spillover effects. Expanding the analysis to include additional economic indicators such as inflation, GDP, and social media sentiment can further refine market predictability and provide deeper insights into asset price dynamics.

Limitations and Future Studies

This study employs an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model to provide a comprehensive framework for analyzing the impact of key commodities and Bitcoin on the S&P 500 index. The choice of OLS over spatial econometric models was primarily due to the study's focus on global asset prices rather than region-specific interactions and the complexity and data constraints associated with spatial modeling in financial markets. For future research, incorporating spatial econometric approaches could offer deeper insights into how regional market dependencies and geographic spillovers influence asset price movements. The OLS model was also chosen to avoid further complicating the analysis due to time constraints and the study's focus on key variables affecting the S&P 500 index, excluding other factors that could also influence the stock market. Therefore, future studies to enhance the model could consider additional parameters such as agricultural product prices, inflation, GDP, and social media trends related to the index in daily and monthly time frames. This expanded approach could significantly improve the predictability of index fluctuations and aid financial market participants in making more accurate investment decisions. Moreover, it is worth noting that future works could apply the proposed model to other country indices.

AI Generative Declaration

The authors used the AI [Chat GPT] to enhance the manuscript's language and readability. Subsequently, they reviewed and refined the content as necessary, accepting complete responsibility for the final version of the published article.

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<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Heydarpour, M. and Mohammadi, E. (2025). Comprehensive Econometric Modeling of Commodity and Cryptocurrency Impacts on the S&P 500 Index. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 12(9), 1337-1354. doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2025.228021</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_228021.html</p>	